

A federated FAIR platform enabling large-scale analysis of high-value cohort data connecting Europe and Canada in personalized health

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ELSI governance model and associated data management plan compliant with the required level of data security and privacy

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Author(s)	Michaela Th. Mayrhofer, Melanie Goisauf, Kaya Akyüz (BBMRI-ERIC), Demetris Avraam and Becca Wilson (ULIV), Morris Swertz, UMCG, Paul Burton (ULIV), Madeleine Murtagh (ULIV/UNEW)
Reviewed by	Tom Bishop, UCAM Sylvain Sebert, Oulu Eleanor Hyde, UMCG
Approved by	Morris Swertz, UMCG
EC Project Officer	Jana Makedonska

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• *Document Abbreviations*

ALLEA	European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities
BBMRI	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
DMP	Data Management Plan
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease
EEA	European Economic Area
EC	European Commission
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
EHDS	European Health Data Space
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Societal Implications
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GAG	Governance Advisory Group
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
ONS	Office for National Statistics
RDA	Research Data Alliance
REC	Research Ethics Committee
RI	Research Infrastructure
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive summary

EUCAN-Connect is committed to connecting existing networks via privacy-protecting data-sharing using ‘federated’ analysis infrastructure made stronger through a unique and flexible governance model by design. Within the EUCAN-Connect project, data processing can be considered as having one of three forms or purposes: (1) federated analysis, especially under DataSHIELD, (2), harmonisation of data for federated analysis, and (3) social science data collection and analysis of Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI). This report describes the integration of ELSI in the governance model and the associated data management and compliance measurements with the required level of data security and privacy integrated for good governance. In particular, this report is concerned with the governance and data management/processing of DataSHIELD.

2. Introduction

2.1. Context

In the context of ‘data’, the term ‘governance’ typically refers to an oversight framework based on policies, processes, and (material and data transfer) agreements that facilitate access to and re-use of data, whilst ensuring respect for fundamental rights, legal requirements and ethical principles. O’Doherty et al. emphasise that ‘a good governance framework should specify the scope of research for which data may be used, including any restrictions based either on the original consent or on guidelines generated for the repository, and specify measures that will be used to mitigate or prevent unintended harms and misuses, including transparent decision-making and oversight processes’ (O’Doherty et al., 2021, p. 5). Consequently, having a solid governance model is imperative when processing health data. This is reflected by a number of recommendations by authoritative bodies such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the World Health Organisation (WHO) on the governance of health data, but also on technical requirements. The OECD, for instance, has highlighted in its *Recommendations on Health Data Governance for the Digital Age* that the opportunities to improve health and health care require the minimisation of misuse of data that are personal by establishing appropriate governance mechanisms (OECD, 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic has placed a spotlight on data sharing and painfully surfaced cross-cutting issues such as legal and ethical considerations (Austin et al., 2020; RDA COVID-19 Working Group, 2020, D7.3). Furthermore, the accumulation of large-scale data, for instance in the case of human genomics, opens up a number of questions into how the existing legal frameworks, guidelines and tools are adapted to the changing understandings and risks of identifiability (Akyüz et al., 2023).

Bernier et al (2023) point out that barriers to inter- and cross-institutional cooperation for partners both within and outside the European Economic Area (EEA) arise from the potential legal liabilities. Certainly, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) shapes the research regimes on the use of personal data and is practically more a directive for data processing for research purposes as Article 89 allows for national derogations, leading to a multitude of country-specific legislation (Slotenberga et al 2021). This results in institutions shifting the responsibilities onto the individual research teams, reminiscent of the fact that the responsibility of the legal departments is to protect the institution rather than to enable research.

Data processing as defined in the GDPR includes the collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination,

restriction, erasure or destruction of personal data for a specific, clearly defined purpose. It is thus a prerequisite of data processing that asking for access to, or usage of, relevant study-specific data, as well as obtaining access or permission to use study-specific data is initiating data processing. This is also the case if data remain on local servers and are processed by the study-specific teams. The goals of ethical, administrative, and technical procedures for data access governance are to establish and implement appropriate legal and technical safeguards to protect the research participants (esp. privacy rights), researchers (e.g. intellectual property rights), and the study and leading organisation itself (e.g., mitigating against reputational risk) as well as entire communities (e.g., ensuring the continuation of public support for entire communities of research) among others (Murtagh et al., 2021; Akyüz et al., 2021).

Data access committees are also responsible for maintaining adherence to regulatory requirements. Regulatory regimes can, when implemented locally, vary from site to site and study to study to various degrees, especially for (transnational) multi-center access procedures. Procedures may include revisions of the project protocol, exchanges with members of scientific or data access committees, and the completion of data transfer or privacy agreements which further involve legal departments. As harmonisation initiatives need to access data from more than one study (often across countries), only a few truly integrated (multistudy) access governance systems exist (Shabani et al, 2021).

Gaining access is always a resource-intensive process. It is thus recommended that data access processes should be initiated as soon as possible (Fortier et al., 2023) and that a dedicated person can guide the process in an informed, sustainable and standardised manner (e.g., data access manager, see: Akyüz et al., 2023). Providing a list of the exact variables required is often requested by the data access committees and may check the variable list against the proposed research question for coherence, thereby following the Article 5(1)(c) of the GDPR ('data minimization'). Preparation of such a list early on can be informed by the result of the harmonisation potential outlined by DataSchema variables and speed up the access procedure and yield more harmonised results (Fortier et al., 2023).

The study of ethical, legal and societal implications (ELSI) reveals and analyses the interrelatedness of emerging life sciences, society and policy in an interdisciplinary manner (Chadwick & Zwart, 2013) and is today well embedded in the H2020 Framework as Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).¹ It strives to enable good governance by design. Looking for ways of addressing ELSI appropriately and timely, scholars have pointed out that the leading principle of data management called FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and

¹ See, for instance the RRI Toolkit of the RRI Tools project (27.06.2023): <https://rri-tools.eu/>

Re-usable data (Wilkins et al., 2016) and proposed by the European Union (EU) to be the case for research data by default² requires additional features. FAIRER for instance, suggests adding ethical and reproducible or equitable and responsible as further characterising elements of this mode of research (Austin, 2020; Murtagh et al., 2021), while FAIR-HEALTH stresses the unified aspects of material and data as a resource requiring quality and privacy preserving elements (Holub et al., 2018). Lastly, the precondition of FAIR is data harmonisation in order to achieve or improve comparability through appropriate documentation and high data quality of different studies (Fortier et al., 2023). Besides FAIR data management, *fair* and responsible data practices also require considering institutional and organisational conditions as well as stakeholder perspectives³ as part of good governance.

EUCAN-Connect is committed to connecting existing networks via a privacy-protecting data-sharing platform made stronger through a unique and flexible governance model by design. It established, for instance, a Governance Advisory Group (GAG) that provided external advice and critical outside stakeholder viewpoints.⁴ Within the EUCAN-Connect project, data processing can be considered as one of three forms or purposes: (1) federated analysis under DataSHIELD, (2), harmonisation of data for federated analysis, and (3) social science data collection and analysis of Ethical, Legal and Social Issues. This report describes the integration of ELSI in the governance model and the associated data management and compliance with the required level of data security and privacy and actions taken. In particular, this report is concerned with the governance and data management/processing of DataSHIELD.

² See for EU's open science policy (27.06.2023): https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

³ EUCAN-Connect captured stakeholder views through semi-structured qualitative (micro-)interviews, ECOUTER and mind-mapping exercises in the context of the annual AGMs and follow up conversations (internal stakeholders, consortium partners) as well as conferences such as the Europe Biobank Week 2019, the Governance Advisory Group and the ELSI EUCAN-Collaboratory network (external stakeholders; e.g., patient advocacy, DataShield users, independent ELSI experts in advisory function and from across other EUCAN projects). Adaptations to the DoA were due to COVID-19 travel restrictions (eg., workshops in Canada did not materialise).

⁴ Also called the Data and Society Governance Advisory Group. It comprises Bartha Knoppers, McGill University (Chair), Alessandro Blassime, University of Zurich, Pascal Borry, University of Leuven, Mark Phillips, McGill University, Barbara Prainsack, University of Vienna, Mark Taylor, University of Melbourne, Sophia Turner, Patient Advocate, Michaela Th. Mayrhofer, BBMRI (WP7 Co-Lead), Madeleine Murtagh, Newcastle/Bristol/Glasgow University (WP7 Co-Lead). Due to COVID-19, only one physical meeting was held and rather bilateral exchanges with members on an ad-hoc basis took place. A final f2f meeting is planned during the closing conference of EUCAN-Connect in Q4/2023.

2.2. Purpose

This deliverable is concerned with the federated analysis under DataSHIELD that leaves all data with the originating cohort study under the data access and governance processes and policies by which that study is bound. It is interrelated with D7.1 Governance Context appraisal and vice versa. This deliverable's (D7.2) major objectives are:

- To assess the integration of ELSI in the governance model
- To assess the integration of the associated data management and compliance with the required level of data security and privacy, especially DataSHIELD.

2.3. Intended Audience

This document is to be used as a reference for:

- all consortium partners of EUCAN-Connect;
- maintainers of participating catalogues;
- current and future consortia embarking on transnational federated data sharing;
- multi-centre cohort studies.

3. Methods

Social science data collection and analysis was undertaken using qualitative methodology, including semi-structured interviews (n=24) and follow up conversations (fact-checking), as well as micro-interviews (n=24), ECOUTER sessions (n=29) and mind mapping exercises during EUCAN-Connect the general assembly meetings. The insights gained, supported by accompanying desktop (literature) research, enabled us to assess and inform EUCAN-Connect (esp. DataSHIELD) on governance aspects.

For the purpose of this deliverable, we decided to further use two elements of accountability as a basis for assessing the modes of governance. It allows us to describe the integration of ELSI elements in the EUCAN-Connect governance model to date and the associated data management as well as its compliance with the required level of data security and privacy, most notably as implemented in DataSHIELD and its risk mitigation measures.

3.1. Accountability

The *European Code of Conduct of Research Integrity* defines ‘**accountability**’ as one of four fundamental principles⁵ for responsible research, which calls for ‘**accountable actions for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring and its wider impacts**’ (ALLEA, 2017). GDPR integrates accountability as a key principle⁶ and “requires that organisations put in place **appropriate technical and organisational measures and be able to demonstrate what they did and its effectiveness when requested**” (European Data Protection Supervisor - EDPS, n.d.).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Data Harmonisation

Harmonisation of data for federated analysis in EUCAN-Connect is undertaken in two ways: 1) by centrally harmonising data from the cohort studies, or 2) providing detailed instructions to the cohort studies for conducting data harmonisation in-house. Where data are centrally harmonised, pooling of data for harmonisation processes will be conducted under the data access policies of the cohort study. A formal data transfer agreement (DTA) with each cohort will bind all data processing activities.

4.2. Governance and Data Management

Governance documents used in EUCAN-Connect that are compatible with the DataSHIELD/federated approach (e.g. the data management plan, a data access agreement and policies for user management) have been developed in WP3. Further internal documents are CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Service).

4.3. DataSHIELD - disclosure protection and governance

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DataSHIELD enables remote statistical analysis on sensitive data in real time while mitigating disclosure risk by an active multi-layer system of disclosure-preventing mechanisms. The

⁵ These principles are: **Reliability** in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources. **Honesty** in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full and unbiased way. **Respect** for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment. **Accountability** for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts. For further information, please see the *European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity* of the *European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities* (27.06.2023): <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>

⁶ Accountability as defined in the GDPR is the guiding principle for initiatives establishing a Code of Conduct under Article 40/41 (e.g., Code of Conduct for Health Research, 27.06.2023: <https://code-of-conduct-for-health-research.eu/>)

purpose of DataSHIELD is to permit researchers to gain access to data for their research by reducing the data governance requirements, and hence any delays in obtaining data access. By design, DataSHIELD has a series of disclosure thresholds and disclosure mitigating policies and processes. DataSHIELD's primary disclosure 'thresholds' are aimed at preventing simple (single-step) approaches to inferential disclosure, including: rules on minimum cell counts in a contingency table (typically 1-5 by default); rules on minimum subset-sizes and rules relating the total number of terms in a regression model to the total number of useable observations in a study.

DataSHIELD is not a federated analysis technology that can be implemented in isolation. There are eleven primary disclosure protections and mitigations in place which either represent formal regulatory and professional conditions for data use, methods embedded in the DataSHIELD software, or are strong recommendations based on best practice relating to implementation. These are as follows:

1. DataSHIELD can only be used in compliance with formal data governance agreements and conditions, managed via user-control settings (including assignment of usernames and passwords for DataSHIELD, datasets approvals are given) based on those conditions. DataSHIELD users working with formally managed data sets – i.e. the vast majority of analysis undertaken on big-Epidemiology and/or health data - are constrained by the conditions of data access awards and by the contractual and cultural expectations to uphold professional standards. Deliberate attempts to identify individuals or to infer the value of variables in the data risks professional censure and sanctions, including dismissal from employment (responsible data use now forms part of academic and health service employment contracts) and denial of future access to managed datasets.
2. DataSHIELD analyses are enacted on a database snapshot, not on the primary/live database for a study.
3. DataSHIELD must be built on robust hardware and all transmissions must be encrypted.
4. The analysis environment server side (R) can only be called via Opal or Armadillo.
5. Only valid characters/functions (via the R Parser) can be passed from client side to the server side.
6. Server side functions block directly disclosive output e.g. print; glm residuals & fitted values.
7. Disclosure traps are built into each function that can call any of the 8 primary disclosure 'thresholds' (e.g. the contingency table function calls the minimum allowable cell size for a contingency table).

8. Only the designated data controller/custodian can change the values of the 8 primary disclosure thresholds for analysis on their DataSHIELD server.
9. All commands on the DataSHIELD server are logged by users so they can later be interrogated if a disclosure event is suspected.
10. DataSHIELD users and deployers are responsible for updating and maintaining their software.
11. As an open-source community, DataSHIELD package developers are responsible for updating and maintaining their packages.

DataSHIELD controls disclosure risk and defines three classes of disclosure protection systems: (i) system protection elements; (ii) analysis protection elements; (iii) governance protection elements.

Avraam et al. (manuscript 2023)⁷ further specify that when a research study has been approved by the data custodian⁸ of a study, researchers are authorised to analyse the harmonised data listed in their approved application:

- Build upon formal governance agreements;
- Only accredited users can login to data servers with user-specific credentials (some consortia also use a central analysis server which is also requires another set of user-specific credentials);
- Access to a specific set of variables is accepted through a data-access procedure which cannot replace or relieve the necessity of an ethics vote in the manner that is suitable locally and internationally;
- Data are pseudonymized or anonymized⁹;
- If the analyst aims to publish the results in a paper, the draft should get the approval from each data owner or respective body (e.g., research ethics committee - REC) or allow for a review period by such stakeholders before submission¹⁰;

⁷ CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

⁸ Data custodian is not a term under the GDPR and has no legal ramifications. A biobank manager is often referred to as 'data custodian'. For a more detailed discussion see, for example, Lavlova et al. (2021).

⁹ In order to comply with pseudonymization criteria specified in Article 4(6) GDPR must be satisfied, anonymised data is outside the scope of the GDPR. For a discussion about pseudonymized and anodized data consider (27.06.2023): https://edps.europa.eu/press-publications/press-news/blog/pseudonymous-data-processing-personal-data-while-mitigating_en

¹⁰ Procedures should be precise and avoid loopholes. loopholes. E.g., any dissemination (not only publications) should be approved by all data controllers.

- Restricted/unrestricted profiles based on which set of functions will be available to which user.

The DataSHIELD infrastructure is compatible with the **Five Safes**¹¹ framework that enables the effective (safe) use of confidential or sensitive data. The framework proposes that data management decisions be considered as responding to questions in five dimensions or key questions (see Table 1) with the final aim to authorise a safe use of data.

Table 1: The Five Safes key questions

- (i) Is this use of the data appropriate? (i.e. is the project safe?)
- (ii) Can the users be trusted to use it in an appropriate manner? (i.e. are the users safe?)
- (iii) Does the access facility limit unauthorised use? (i.e. are the settings safe?)
- (iv) Is there a disclosure risk in the data itself? (i.e. are the data safe?)
- (v) Are the statistical results non-disclosive? (i.e. are the outputs safe?)

In relation to DataSHIELD, Avraam et al. (manuscript 2023) conclude that questions (i)-(ii) are controlled by project-specific governance agreements, whereas questions (iv)-(v) are controlled by the system’s architecture and the statistical disclosure controls of the analytical functions, while question (iii) is controlled by a mixture of the protection elements related to governance processes, the entire system and the analytical functions.

Moreover, Avraam et al. argue that a number of additional statistical and computational disclosure control approaches have been recently prototyped or are under development, to mitigate the risk of inferential and contextual based disclosures. New developments will open up the flexibility of DataSHIELD use with datasets that have more stringent data protection requirements and will provide real-time solutions to support the existing data governance processes to mitigate the risks. New elements include data anonymization (e.g. adding noise

¹¹ The Five Safes is a set of principles which enable data services to provide safe research access to data. The framework originated from the UK Office for National Statistics and was developed by them and other data providers in the 2010s according to the UK Data Service, see (27.06.2023): <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-the-five-safes-framework/>. Similar concepts and terminologies are called Secure Processing Environments (SPE) or Trusted Research Environments (TRE). In Europe, the differences and similarities are currently debated among experts. Consider, for example the discussions of the TEHDAS project in relation to SPE’s and the realisation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS), which uses SPEs more generic, see: (27.06.2023): <https://tehdas.eu/news/european-health-data-specialists-discuss-the-ecosystem-of-the-european-health-data-space/>.

on the data to prevent differencing attacks), data synthesis (enabling generation of synthetic data¹², differential privacy and homomorphic encryption.

5. Conclusion

Using the principle of ‘**accountability**’ both in the ethical sense as a key principle for responsible research (Code of conduct of the *European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities* - ALLEA) and data protection (GDPR), this report assessed the governance set up of DataSHIELD, most notably in relation to secure processing and disclosure risks. It concludes that DataSHIELD adheres to the Five Safes framework and is solid in its governance set up.

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¹² See (27.06.2023): <https://www.datashield.org/help/community-packages/dssynthetic-package>

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